

LEVELS OF UNDERSTANDING A ARTWORK AND THEIR POSSIBLE CONTRADICTORY COLLISION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the difficulties of understanding a literary text, since the understanding of a literary text moves from verbal to substantive, the combination of which gives a logical understanding; from it, the movement is directed to understanding matters, goals, and subject. In this direction, the process of perception of the actual and emotional-artistic content of the work takes place.

emotional-artistic, complex, contradictory process, clarification, perception,

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There are two levels in the content of a work of art: one of them is the actual (logical) content, the other is emotional and artistic. That is why the perception and understanding of a work is a complex and often contradictory process, during which many students achieve only the first level of assimilation of the content of the work. The understanding of a literary text moves from the verbal to the subject, the combination of which gives a logical understanding, movement from him is directed to understanding the matters, goals, subject. In this approximate direction, the process of perception of the actual and emotional-artistic content of the work takes place. Understanding the first level of a work (its actual content) occurs mainly through the explanation (clarification) of its verbal-conceptual material. Here a logical activity takes place, requiring largely common sense, primarily to clarify the meaning of words, the meaning of concepts, realities and reality. However, when studying fiction, it is necessary to raise the student to the second level of perception (understanding) of the work, to the level of understanding its emotional and artistic content. Here the teacher tries to use such methods of working with a literary text that deepen his emotional perception, enrich such perception when the student penetrates the artistic fabric of the work.

The process of understanding is not only complex, but also contradictory. Here, a contradiction is possible between the perception of the actual (logical) and emotional and artistic content of the work. The first stage of perception, as we know, leads to an understanding of the logical factual content of the work. To step only here means to enter into a contradictory attitude towards subsequent work on a literary text, moreover, to show it does. Achieving logical understanding is not addressed to the emotional activity of students, it is not based on the maturing and development of their creative imagination, what we call the culture of reading works of art of the word. However, it is impossible to bypass the first stage of perception, it is the basis for achieving the main goal of studying fiction - its emotional and artistic perception.

This is where difficulties arise: "There are two difficulties first, so that the children understand the necessary work and, second, so that the children feel it - in practice they often contradict one another. Lengthy detailed explanations of a poetic work weaken its impression on the senses, and on the other hand, the impression on the senses is possible only when the necessary work is completely understandable. The contradiction of the two goals of understanding (two stages) in school practice takes on another form - contradiction between the tasks of analyzing a work of art. Often, the analysis comes down only to expanding the knowledge of students (the nature of the character, the ideological meaning of the work, its historical and literary significance, etc.). In other words, analysis is only an abstract-logical activity and does not affect the emotional side of the student's personality in any way. Meanwhile, a genuine analysis of the work, evoking the intellectual activity of students, must at the same time deepen and enrich their emotional perception of a literary text, enrich their emotional world. There is only one way out - the correct combination in the educational process of activities to reveal the verbal-conceptual (logical) and emotional-affective content of the work, constant attention to enriching the knowledge of students and the emotional richness of their personality.

LITERATURE

Shklyomachenko, E. R. Modern methods of assessing learning outcomes. *Young scholar*, 02, 888-898.

V. A. Mikhalev. Methods of teaching literature in secondary school M. "Enlightenment", 1991 (ed. "Methodology as a science").

Khodjanzanova, G. (2000). Using interactive methods in literature classes. *ISPI Scientific Publications Archive*, 103.

Parsharova, I. (2000). The use of innovative technologies in the classroom for the development of speech in non-linguistic groups. *ISPI Scientific Publications Archive*, 1003.

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